

Assessing Effectiveness of Broadcast Media Messages in Addressing Environmental issues in Imo State

Igbokwe, Basilia Nkemdilim (PhD)

Department of Humanities
Federal Polytechnic Nekede Owerri, Imo State
bigbokwe@fpno.edu.ng
+2348037103275

Ejiogu, Felicia Ijeoma (Corresponding Author)

Department Of Mass Communication
Federal Polytechnic Nekede Owerri, Imo State
ejioguij@gmail.com
+2348032740356

Olewuike Evans C.

Department Of Mass Communication
Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri
olewuikee@yahoo.com
+2347039520606

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Abstract

The study examined Imo residents' perspectives on the effectiveness of broadcast media messages in addressing environmental issues. The objectives include: ascertaining Imo residents level of exposure to environmental-related messages on the broadcast media, ascertaining primary language used to communicate environmental issues, determining Imo state residents' level of knowledge on environmental issues, and assessing their perceptions about the influence of broadcast media in promoting environmentally friendly behaviors. The study was anchored on the theory of perception. The mixed research design, comprising survey and in-depth interview methods, was adopted, with the population of residents in Imo State estimated at 5,459,300. Krejcie and Morgan sample size table was used to derive a sample size of 384. The multi-stage cluster sampling technique was adopted to select participants for the study. A structured questionnaire and interview guide served as the instruments for data collection. Analysis of data involved descriptive and inferential statistics. Qualitative data was analysed thematically. The Chi-square test was employed as the statistical tool, and the analysis was conducted using SPSS. Result revealed that the majority being 48% of the respondents listen to the radio or watch the television whenever they feel like doing so. Findings showed that 50% of the respondents receive environmental-related information over-the-air radio while 48% access similar messages on television through the INTERNET. Results indicated that 52% sometimes receive information on global warming and climate change impacts, and 53% are sometimes exposed to poor waste management. 66% of respondents stated that environmental information is delivered in standard English, and half of the respondents preferred English for communicating environmental issues.

43% said broadcast media messages has partially influenced their understanding of human activities causing environmental degradation. The study further found that 78% believed that broadcast media messages create environmental consciousness. Besides, 48% were of the view that broadcast messages do not foster environmentally sustainable practices. Recommendations arising from the findings of the study include that environmental issues reportage on radio and television should become more regularly through their various channels. Secondly that the broadcast media should endeavour to utilise the audience most preferred language(s) to communicate environmental-related issues, partnership between the broadcast media and environmental experts was recommended in order to boost environmental best practices.

Keywords: Assessing, Addressing, Broadcast Media, Environmental Issues, Messages

Introduction

The indispensibility of the environment as the background, or setting for both the biotic and the abiotic gives credence to Anatsui and Adekanye, (2021:31) assertion that, “Man is environment dependent, as such, there is need for man to be environment conscious”. However, Omari et al. (2021) noted that the activities and interactions of the various components of the environment influence the environmental conditions. Thus, causing either favourable or unfavourable changes to the environment (Ashhar, et al. n.d). The negative environmental impacts remain an international and domestic concern with its attendant socio-economic challenges attracting intervention by the media and other stakeholders in Nigeria including Imo state (Piyapong and Surapong 2020; Donna, et al. 2021; Anyanwu et al. 2019).

Nigeria has adopted several interventions to tackle environmental issues which include but not limited to the National Environmental Standards and Regulatory Enforcement Agency (NESREA) with the responsibility to enforce environmental regulatory laws and policies in the country (Ministry of Information, Office of Environmental Assessment 2018)). Besides, the initiatives such as Nigeria Erosion and Watershed Management Project (NEWMAP) with a major objective to address a multi-dimensional scale menace of gully erosion in the south east with Imo state as one of the beneficiaries . The Ecological Fund interventions by the Federal government solely devoted to funding ecological projects to mitigate serious environmental problems (Ecological fund office,2019; Kareem, 2022). At the international scene, Denchak (2021) said the Paris Agreement was signed by many countries including Nigeria with the aim to limit global temperature rise and climate change through carbon emissions reduction.

There is the need to educate the public on the imperative of engaging in practices that can enhance environmental health and sustainability in Nigeria including Imo state. This could be possible through media advocacy and campaigns on issues such as poor waste management and the alarming climate change impacts such as drought, flood/erosion, unsafe water, among others (Chukwuebuni et al. 2023; Abdujabbarov, 2023; Rai-Sharma, 2018; Jharotia, 2018). Television as a broadcast media is a widely accessible and influential medium that offers vital information on development issues(Ucheanya, et al.). In the same vein the radio is a pervasive media with numerous communication strengths capable of influencing knowledge and action (Njoku, et al.2023)

language used to convey information and raise awareness on environmental issues such as climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss, remains insufficiently examined. There is therefore the

need to rigorously assess how well these traditional approaches engage audiences and facilitate meaningful understanding of environmental concerns.

Besides, there is limited empirical evidence on the effectiveness of radio and television in raising environmental consciousness in Imo State. This study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge by providing research-based insights into the place of broadcast media in raising environmental awareness. The outcome will provide insights into the role of environmental broadcast reporting in promoting responsible practices for a sustainable environment, with implications for SDG 11, which targets Sustainable Cities and Communities."

Statement of the Problem

Many states in Nigeria, including Imo State, continue to grapple with a range of environmental challenges arising from climate change impacts, poor waste management practices, and other unsustainable human activities. Issues such as flooding, pollution, and indiscriminate waste disposal have persisted, compromising access to safe drinking water, threatening food security, and deteriorating overall public health. The continuous degradation of the environment remains a major source of concern.

Furthermore, the current era is characterized by widespread information disorder within the communication ecosystem, driven largely by advancements in information and communication technologies. This situation, combined with the increasing need for strategic media intervention on environmental matters, creates uncertainty regarding the quantity, quality, and clarity of environmental messages disseminated through broadcast media, particularly radio and television. It is unclear whether these messages are adequate, accurate, and compelling enough to influence and promote environmentally friendly attitudes and behaviors among the public.

Against this backdrop, this study seeks to assess the effectiveness of broadcast media in addressing environmental issues through awareness raising with a specific focus on residents in Imo State.

Objectives of the Study

1. determine the extent to which residents in Imo State are exposed to broadcast media messages on environmental issues.
2. ascertain the language(s) in which residents of Imo State receive information concerning environmental issues.
3. assess the level of knowledge of Imo State residents on environmental issues as influenced by broadcast media.
4. examine Imo residents' perceptions of the effectiveness of broadcast media in influencing environmentally responsible behaviours.

Hypothesis

The researchers proposed that;

Ho: There is no significant difference between the language used in communicating environmental issues and the adoption of environmental best practices in Imo State.

Literature Review

Mass Media and Environmental Issues

Mass media refer to the devices that enable transmission of information to a large scattered heterogeneous audience including; radio, television, print, film, internet, social media platforms, cable, satellites etc (Iwasaki and Hendricks, 2023). The mass media including the radio and television through the role of surveillance covers wide range of subjects in order to create awareness on various issues including environmental related issues (Junsheng et al., 2019). However, environmental issues are the challenges facing humanity majorly caused by the alteration of the natural functioning of the ecosystem consequent upon anthropogenic activities (Chi and Lee, 2022). Through sensitisation the media citizens can be sensitised on the relevance of certain initiative or project geared towards addressing environmental issues, (Dorji, 2018; Jharotia, 2018)).

Further, through different styles, framing or formats of programming the broadcast media can enhance understanding of environmental issues and how they impact every aspect of life (Junsheng et al., and Omari et al. 2019). Besides, Abdujabbarovna (2023) explained that; support for environmental policies can be encouraged, public concern can also be galvanized and attitude influenced through media coverage.

Empirical Studies on Media and Environmental issues

Sanusi et al. (2025) assessed how effective radio campaigns have been able to address the flooding incidents through awareness raising and mobilising members of the Lamodi community in Offa Kwara state towards. The study was anchored on agenda setting theory. A descriptive survey design was adopted in the study to study 400 residents of Lamodi. Findings revealed 75% of respondents attesting to being aware of campaigns. Over 90% of respondents rated the campaigns as effective or very effective in community mobilisation. The study recommended that local government areas and other stakeholders continue leveraging radio as a platform for flood awareness and education while efforts should be made to diversify the radio campaign content.

Nwokedi and Okechukwu-Eze (2024) in their study examined the effectiveness of broadcast media messages in advocating for intervention in environmental degradation in the Alor-Uno community, Enugu State. The mixed-method was adopted to survey 370 residents of the Alor-Uno community and interviews was conducted with key stakeholders. The findings indicated that the majority of respondents (89.6%) have access to radio and television, with 83.2% reporting exposure to environmental messages among other findings. The study concluded that broadcast media is an effective tool in addressing environmental degradation in rural communities but recommended enhancing the media's approach by considering local contents and involving community stakeholders.

Moreover, Chukwuebuni *et al.*, (2023) in their study examined the mass media role in the prevention of environmental pollution with a focus on Etsako West local government area of Edo state. The study employed the survey method and a sample size of 400. Whereas the instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. Data was analysed using tables and simple percentage. Finding revealed lack of environmental communication or campaign on the mass media therefore,

it was recommended that the media should endeavour to carry out communication campaigns on environmental issues.

Similarly, Banjo and Obun-Andy (2023) employed the survey method to examined Ogun residents on the media's contribution in raising awareness on environmental issues using a sample size of 200 respondents. A multi-stage sampling technique involving stratified, simple random and purposive technique was employed. Likert- type rating scale guided the data collection instrument. Analysis of data was done using SPSS 25.0. Result of the hypothesis indicated that there is a significant relationship between environmental education and media awareness role. The researcher's recommendations included; improvement on the awareness raising role of the media.

In the same vein, Nnadiukwu and Omeje (2019) investigated effectiveness of the mass media campaigns against environmental degradation in Nigeria with a focus on Enugu state. The study used the survey method and a sample size of 385 was derived using Australian online calculator. Purposive sampling technique was used to select participants. Based on the findings, the study concluded that the public are aware of environmental issues in Enugu through the information they receive from the mass media and that the campaign against environmental degradation on the mass media have been effective in Enugu. The study recommended among other things that the broadcast media should come up with special programmes dedicated to environmental sustainability.

Relatedly, Anyanwu et al. (2024) employed a descriptive survey to investigate the effectiveness of digital communication in tackling environmental degradation in Owerri. The Australian sample size calculator was used to select 385 participants from the 983,000 estimated population. Data was collected via a questionnaire, and analysed using percentages. Results showed that digital communication is used to circulate information on the dangers of environmental degradation in Owerri, Imo state to a low extent among other findings. Based on the findings the recommendation was that digital communication on environment should be more regular and more engaging.

Furthermore, Obuah (2017) evaluated the River State waste management agency's communication strategies to determine their effectiveness in promoting residents' compliance. The survey design was adopted, utilizing a multi-stage cluster sampling technique, the study selected 181 RIWAMA staff members and 385 Port Harcourt residents. Data collected using the questionnaires indicated that residents demonstrated a relatively high level of awareness of RIWAMA's waste management campaigns. However, this awareness did not translate into a corresponding level of compliance with proper waste disposal practices. Recommendations were made based on the results.

Theoretical Framework

The Perception theory that underpins this study originated from early studies demonstrating that individuals are selective in the media they consume and the content they attend to. Over time, the theory has expanded into a broader explanation of how audiences interpret messages. A major foundation was laid by Lazarsfeld and colleagues in the 1940s, whose work emphasized selective exposure. This was later advanced by scholars such as Katz and Lazarsfeld, who introduced the related ideas of selective perception, selective attention, and selective retention. Subsequent contributions, especially Berelson and Steiner's 1964 work, offered a core definition of perception as the process of selecting, organizing, and interpreting sensory information as explained in Anaeto et al., (2012) cited in Okeya-Olayinka et al.(2021).The perception theory is relevant to this study

because it provides a means for understanding why broadcast media messages may be effective or ineffective. It helps explain the psychological processes that shape how residents of Imo State access, interpret, and act upon environmental information delivered through radio and television.

Method

The study employed a mixed research design, combining the survey method and in-depth interviews to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. The survey method was considered appropriate since the study involved collecting data on the knowledge and perceptions of the study variables. The population of the study consists of the residents of Imo State, based on a population estimated at 5,459,300 as captured in Thomas (2022). Krejcie and Morgan sample size table was used to arrive at the sample size of 384 at 95% confidence level and 5.0 margin of error while, the sample size for the in-depth interview was based on the saturation principle.

Multi-stage cluster sampling technique was employed as follows;

Stage 1: The three Senatorial zones, Imo East, Imo North, and Imo West, were represented in the study.

Stage 2: A Simple random sampling technique through the sampling frame was used to select two local government areas from each senatorial zone. This culminated in the selection of Owerri West, Ahiazu Mbaise, Obowo, Onuimo, Ngwerre, and Orsu Local Government Areas.

Stage 3: Convenience and snowball sampling approaches were employed to select participants from the chosen L.G.A.s for the survey. Presenters of Imo Broadcasting Corporation (IBC) and NTA Owerri and some rural broadcast media audience were purposively selected for the in-depth interviews based on the criteria that participants must be 27 years and above and must be an employee of any government ministry, agency or parastatals (retired or in active service). This is because the researchers believe that this category of individuals can easily understand the relevance of the study and will be able to cooperate with the researchers and the research assistants.

The instrument for data collection for the quantitative data was a structured questionnaire while the interview guide was for the qualitative data. About 640 copies of questionnaire were distributed based on 60% response rate through whatsapp platforms, private chats and also face-to-face contacts. The same was obtainable for the qualitative data collection. The Quantitative data analysis employed descriptive statistics involving frequency counts and percentages while the Chi square formed the inferential statistical tool which was guided by the SPSS software. The qualitative data employed thematic analysis.

Results

At the end of data collection, data were collated and cleaned leading to selection of 384 respondents with valid responses.

Table 1

Sex

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Female	283	74%
Male	101	26%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey, 2025

The result in Table 1 indicates that the majority (74%) of the respondents are female.

Table 2

How Often Respondents Listen to Radio or Watch Television

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Weekly	100	26%
Daily	66	17%
Whenever I want	183	48%
Monthly	35	9%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey, 2025

Data as presented in table 2 show that 48% representing the majority of the respondents listen to the radio or watch the television whenever they wish.

Table 3

Radio Channel on which Respondents Receive Information on Environmental Issues

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Online Radio	148	38%
Over the -Air -Radio channels	190	50%
A& C	27	7%
All of the above	19	5%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey, 2025

Finding presented in table 3 reveals that 50% being the majority of the respondents receive information on environmental issues through the terrestrial transmission

Table 4

Television Channel on which Respondents Receive Information on Environmental Issues

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Over -the- Air channels	48	13%
Cable TV	20	5%
Online TV Channel	185	48%
All of the above	117	30%
Others	14	4%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey, 2025

Result in Table 4 shows that 48% representing the majority of the respondents receive information about environmental issues through internet television channels.

Table 5

How often Respondents Receive Broadcast Media Information on Global Warming and Climate Change Impacts Like extreme Heat, flooding, Drought, etc

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Rarely	28	7%
Sometimes	200	52%
Occasionally	96	25%
Always	60	16%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey, 2025

Data as presented in table 5 indicates that 52% being the majority of the respondents from time to time receive information on extreme Heat, flooding, drought from the broadcast media

Table 6

How often Respondents Receive Information on Broadcast Media about Poor Waste Management and Pollution

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Rarely	30	8%
Sometimes	204	53%
Occasionally	58	15%
Always	92	24%
Total	384	100%

Source; Online and Field Survey, 2025

Finding on table 6 reveals the reception of information about poor waste management, pollution, heavy traffic among others received sometimes on the broadcast media by the majority (53%) of the respondents.

Table 7

Major language used in Communicating Environmental Issues on Radio and Television

OPTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Central Igbo	28	7%
Standard English	252	66%
Pidgin	80	21%
Igbo Dialect	18	4%
Others	6	2%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey 2025

Data presented in table 7 reveal that the major language used in communicating environmental issues in the radio and television as evident in the responses by 66% of the respondents forming the majority.

Table 8

Preferred Language for the Broadcasting of Environmental Issues

OPTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Central Igbo	55	14%
Standard English	192	50%
Pidgin	83	22%
Igbo Dialects	38	10%
Others	16	4%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey, 2025

Result in table 8 indicates that the majority (50%) of the respondents prefer to receive information on environmental issues in standard English language.

Table 9

Improvement of respondents' knowledge on Global Warming and Climate Change impacts as result of Information Received on Broadcast Media.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	81	21%
Agree	92	24%
Disagree	198	52%
Strongly disagree	13	3%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey,2025

Findings as presented in table 9 show that 52% of the respondents representing the majority rejected the position that their level of knowledge on global warming and climate change has improved due to information reported on the broadcast media. Meanwhile only 45% of the

respondents reported improvement of knowledge on the subject matter as a result of the exposure to messages received through the broadcast media.

Table 10

Broadcast Media Reports Improving Respondents' Understanding that Human Activities are Responsible for Environmental Degradation.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
True	134	34%
Partially	166	43%
False	77	20%
Not sure	7	2%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey, 2025

Data in Table 10 reveal that the majority (43%) of the respondents somewhat admitted that the broadcast media has improved their understanding of the fact that human activities contribute to environmental degradation. However, 34% totally affirmed the assertion.

Table 11

Radio and Television Messages Help to Create Environmental Consciousness

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	300	78%
Agree	68	17%
Disagree	6	2%
Strongly disagree	10	3%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey 2025

Findings in Table 11 show that the majority (78%) of the respondents accepted that the radio and television messages contribute in creating environmental consciousness in society

Table 12

Broadcast Media Reports on Environmental Issues play a Significant Role in Fostering Environmental Best Practices.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	100	26%
Agree	66	17%
Disagree	183	48%
Strongly Disagree	35	9%
Total	384	100%

Source: Online and Field Survey 2025

The result in Table 12 indicates that 48% representing the majority of the respondents are of the view that broadcast media messages or reports do not necessarily foster environmental best practices.

Qualitative Data

Themes from IBC and NTA Respondents

Comprehensive Media Coverage of Environmental Issues

The staff of IBC and NTA noted that their stations engage in extensive coverage of global, continental, and local environmental concerns. While referencing broader issues like UN and AU positions on climate change, their reports focus mainly on waste management, pollution, flooding, and disease outbreaks within Imo State and beyond. Reporters are regularly deployed to markets, industries, schools, and homes to assess waste management practices, which are later presented in various programmes.

Multi-platform Dissemination Strategies

Environmental messages are transmitted through diverse platforms including Over-the-Air broadcasts, satellite, Facebook, and YouTube, ensuring wide reach. Programmes use straight news, documentaries, discussions, interviews, and vox pop formats to communicate environmental information. The use of English, Pidgin, and Igbo was also found.

Media Support for Government Environmental Agencies

IBC actively report and promotes the initiatives of the Ministry of Environment and ENTRACO, particularly in waste management. Programmes explaining ENTRACO's operations have increased public understanding and improved compliance with waste disposal guidelines.

Audience Engagement and Behavioural Influence

Audience participation is encouraged with listeners and viewers asking questions and contributing during live and online programmes. High engagement in programmes such as "Issues of the Moment" shows growing public interest in flooding, waste management, and pollution. Media messages—especially on NTA—have inspired residents to adopt better environmental practices, contributing to improved waste disposal behaviour across the state(see Appendix I).

Interview with respondents from the selected Local Government Areas

Broadcast Media as Primary Information Source

Respondents consistently rely on the radio for environmental information, citing frequent listening and accessibility in both English and Igbo. Television is secondary and mostly accessed through mobile phones or social media.

Awareness of Environmental Hazards

Respondents repeatedly mention flooding, heavy rains, thunderstorms, and bush burning, showing high exposure to environmental risk information.

Waste Management Concerns

There is strong awareness of indiscriminate waste disposal, foul odours from landfills and drainage blocked by refuse, especially during the rainy season. Radio discussions from time to time focus on urging agencies to maintain street and drainage cleanliness.

Multi-Channel Media Exposure

Environmental messages reach residents through radio, TV, Facebook, and online channels, indicating a blend of traditional and digital media access to environmental messages.

Place of Local Radio Stations in Environmental Education

Stations such as Bizzi Body, Ecko FM, and Hot FM were identified as active in discussing environmental issues, reinforcing radio's contribution in shaping public understanding and behaviour.

Test of Hypothesis

H_0

There is no significant difference between the language used in communicating environmental issues and the adoption of environmental best practices in Imo State.

A significant difference was found in the language used in communicating environmental issues on radio and television in Imo State (see Appendix III). This implies that some languages, notably Standard English, are used far more frequently than others (like Igbo dialects or Pidgin) in environmental communication. Hence, the language of communication significantly influences the adoption of environmental best practices, likely because messages in English reach a wider or more educated audience.

Discussion of Findings

1) Extent of Exposure to Environmental Issues on the Broadcast Media.

Result indicated that Majority (48%) of the respondents listen to the radio or watch the television any time they choose. Data analysis showed that 50% being the majority of the respondents receive information on environmental issues through terrestrial broadcasting. Also found was that 48% receive information about environmental issues through INTERNET-based television channels. Finding revealed that the majority (52%) of the respondents from time to time receive information on extreme heat, flooding, drought etc from the broadcast media.

While 53% sometimes receive information about poor waste management and pollution. The qualitative data confirms that people listen to or view radio and television broadcasts. The implication of the findings is that respondents are aware of certain environmental issues. The result is consistent with Nwokedi and Okechukwu-Eze (2024) who found that many individuals have access to radio and television and at the same vein exposed to environmental issues. The findings is in line with Nnadiukwu and Omeje (2019) that found that the public is aware of environmental issues. It resonates with Anyanwu et al. (2024) that digital communication is used to circulate

information on the threats of environmental degradation. It contradicts Chukwuebuni *et al.*, (2023) that revealed lack of environmental communication on the mass media.

2. Language(s) Used for Broadcasting Environmental Issues

Finding revealed that 66% of the respondents affirmed that the language mostly used in broadcasting environmental issues is the English language which was also found to be the majority (50%) of the respondents preferred language to receive information on environmental issues. The interview with IBC and NTA staff confirmed that information on environmental issues are disseminated using English language. The implication of the result is that the majority of the respondents are comfortable with the use of English language for environmental information dissemination. The findings contradicts Nwokedi and Okechukwu-Eze (2024) suggestions for the adoption of local languages in communicating environmental issues. Results support framing theory which supports language as a strategic tool for presenting information on various issues to achieve target goal.

3) Knowledge Level on Environmental-related Issues

Analysis of data revealed that 52% being the majority of the respondents rejected the idea that their level of knowledge on global warming/climate change mitigation strategies has improved due to information reported on the broadcast media. Meanwhile, finding showed that 45% accepted the improvement of their knowledge on the subject matter as a result of the exposure to messages on the broadcast media. Findings revealed that the majority (43%) of the respondents somewhat admitted that the broadcast media has improved their understanding of the fact that human activities contribute to environmental degradation. Where 34% totally confirmed the assertion. The Qualitative data buttressed the findings by pointing out the engagement of radio and television in disseminating information on environmental issues. The 45% respondents that attested to improved knowledge based on exposure to broadcast media messages is related to Junsheng *et al.*, (2019) who explained that the broadcast media through various programmes formats can enhance understanding of environmental issues and their impacts. The result resonates with Sanusi *et al.* (2025) findings that radio campaigns significantly increased public awareness of flood-related issues in Offa, Kwara state. Finding buttressed Banjo and Obun-Andy (2023) that showed a significant relationship between environmental education and media awareness role.

4.) Perception on the Influence of Broadcast Media in Addressing Environmental Issues.

Results showed that the majority (78%) of the respondents support that information disseminated through the radio and television contribute in creating environmental consciousness. The result is in line with Banjo and Obun-Andy (2023) that found a significant relationship between environmental education and media awareness role. It is in consonance with Nnadiukwu and Omeje (2019) finding that the public are aware of environmental issues in Enugu through the information they receive from the mass media. Result indicating that 48% of the respondents view that broadcast media messages or reports do not necessarily foster environmental best practices is inconsistent with Nwokedi and Okechukwu-Eze (2024) observation that revealed motivation for environmental responsibility as a result of awareness raised through broadcast media messages. Besides, it contradicts (Jharotia; 2018; Donna *et al.*, 2021) submission that broadcast media can amplify the voices of environmental advocates, spur best practices. and persuade the public to

support mitigation and conservation initiatives. The findings are in tandem with the qualitative data.

Discussion of Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the language used in communicating environmental issues and the adoption of environmental best practices in Imo State.

The Chi-Square result ($\chi^2 = 540.16$, $df = 4$, $p < .05$) revealed a statistically significant difference in the languages used for communicating environmental issues to various audiences, including those in Imo State. This outcome can be interpreted through the lens of framing theory, which posits that the way information is presented influences how audiences perceive, interpret, and act upon it. The findings are not consistent with the observations of Nwokedi and Okechukwu-Eze (2024), who advocate for the increased adoption of indigenous languages in environmental communication. Their study emphasizes that local languages carry cultural nuances and shared meanings that enhance message relatability and emotional connection.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Radio and television operators should create more space to accommodate regular reporting of vast environmental-related issues.
2. Stakeholders in the media industry should leverage various radio and television broadcasting formats and channels in both terrestrial and internet-based to diversify messages on environmental issues.
3. Producers and Presenters should endeavour to reach their target audience in their most preferred language(s) in communicating environmental issues.
4. Media organisations should partner with environmental experts/agencies to disseminate credible information that can boost action.

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Supplementary Information

Credit Authorship Contribution Statement

Igbokwe Basilia Nkemdilim: Conceptualisation, Data Curation, Review and Editing, Supervision.

Ejiogu Felicia Ijeoma: Conceptualization, Original Drafting, Methodology, Designing of instruments, Data curation, Manuscript drafting.

Evans Olewuike C: Literature Review, Data Curation, Data Analysis.

Informed Consent Statement

Participation in the research was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was duly obtained from all participants.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests that influenced the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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